

Investigation into Learning Attitudes Among Intermediate Economics Students in Oyo Educational Zone

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Abstract:

This study delved into learning attitudes among intermediate economics students in senior secondary schools in Oyo educational zone via psychological constructs of cognitive skills, affection for learning, attached value, efforts, and difficulties in learning. While age and gender served as moderator variables. The composite contributions of cognitive skills and affection for learning, attached value and effort, and interest and difficulties in learning served as predictors for learning attitude. Moreover, the composite contributions and influence of variables and their relation to learning attitude, as well as the influence of gender and age, were explored. A

survey research study with the use of an adapted ESLAS questionnaire was administered to 355 respondents, and the data was analyzed with descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential (t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA)) statistics. The results showed a significant influence of gender, while age was not statistically significant on learning attitude. The composite contributions of cognitive skills and affection; attached value and efforts; and interest and difficulties in learning as predictors of learning attitude were significant among intermediate economics students. In conclusion, the prediction of learning attitude implies that there is a great need for students to be proactive in learning, as this would improve their cognitive skills, affection, attached value, efforts, and interest in learning while reducing difficulties and challenges to the barest minimum.

Keywords: *Cognitive skills, affection, attached value, efforts, interest, difficulties, learning, Learning attitude, Economics students.*

Introduction

By definition, learning is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, attitudes, or behaviors through studying, practicing, and experiencing new information or concepts. It involves the ability to absorb, understand, and apply new knowledge effectively. Learning, then, gives anyone the opportunity to acquire knowledge and skills to operate effectively within society (Oladimeji, 2023). Learning provides the basis for a wholesome life. On the other hand, attitude refers to an individual's overall evaluation,

perception, or feelings towards a person, object, event, or situation. It is shaped by various factors, including personal beliefs, values, experiences, and social influences. In line with Mokoro, Wambiya, and Aloba (2014), attitude is an imaginary thought that indicates a person's abhorrence or preferences towards a thing. It could be unbiased, negative, or positive. Attitude is a sensation, demeanor, approach, or circumstance concerning a thing or person. It is a course or an inclination, especially of the mind, affecting how we look at things. It affects not

only our personal relationships but also our professional interactions and academic pursuits.

Fatoba and Aladejana (2014) described attitude as the human tendency to organize thought, emotions, and behaviors towards a psychological object. It is an antecedent that serves as an input or stimulus that activates actions and likewise affects the degree of their retention. That is why Kidane and Worth (2013) posited that it is a veritable tool to comprehend and foresee individuals' responses to an article or change and how conduct can be effected. Attitude serves as a medium for connecting and disconnecting from an object based on its pre-knowledge. While attitudes continue to change, individuals will, in general, adopt another type of demeanor and change old lifestyles when they are open to innovative encounters and data (Adesina and Akinbobola, 2005). When an attitude is embraced, it assists with framing the abilities the individual has as an individual (Ibeh, Onah, Umahi, Ugwuonah, Nnachi, and Ekpe, 2013).

The attitude of learners towards learning is critical to the process of acquiring knowledge. Although learning is a medium through which knowledge and skills are learned, an encouraging attitude has a far-reaching effect on the value attached to it by a student. Learning can only be attained through the possession of optimistic attitudes. Learning attitude, then, refers to an individual's mindset and approach towards learning. It involves the willingness and eagerness to acquire new knowledge, skills, and understanding. Many researchers who examined students learning attitudes have emphasized the significance of students' attitudinal variables as performance predictors among students (Adodo and Gbore, 2012). This means that attitude forms the basis of the academic and learning achievements of any student. Adodo and Gbore (2012) thought that students' attitudes are probably a critical part of any good clarification of levels of learning in school's subjects. A positive learning attitude includes being open-minded, being proactive, taking initiative, and being persistent in the face of challenges. The findings of Festus and Ekpete (2012) corroborated Adodo and Gbore's (2012) finding that students' learning attitudes and interests

could play an extensive role in enhancing performances. This implies that a positive predisposition of learners could fast-track their learning speed and could be the most significant predictor for assessing students' success. Therefore, students' beliefs, feelings, emotions, or intended behaviors must be mobilized towards the right learning attitude.

Literature Review

Age and Learning Attitude

Age and learning attitude are two important factors that can significantly affect a person's educational journey (Zöllner and Dennerlein, 2015). Firstly, let us explore the role of age. Age can affect learning in various ways. In early childhood, children have a remarkable capacity to absorb and rapidly acquire new knowledge and skills. They are naturally curious, have a higher level of openness, and are generally more receptive to new information. Thus, educational experiences at this stage focus on stimulating their curiosity, providing a nurturing environment, and utilizing appropriate teaching methods such as play-based learning. As children progress into their teenage years, they may start developing different interests, passions, and even challenges related to their identity. This stage requires educators to understand the individual needs and preferences of their students. Teenagers might benefit from more interactive and engaging teaching methods that cater to their evolving cognitive abilities, social interests, and desire for independence.

Moving on to adulthood, learning attitudes can become more influenced by personal motivations, life experiences, and the perception of the relevance of learning to their lives. Adults often have goals that are more specific and a greater understanding of the practical applications of their learning. They may be motivated by career advancements, personal growth, or acquiring new skills for hobbies and interests. Now, let us discuss the concept of learning attitude. Learning attitude refers to an individual's mindset, beliefs, and approach towards learning (Lai and Kwan, 2012). It

encompasses elements such as motivation, perseverance, self-discipline, curiosity, and the ability to embrace challenges.

A positive learning attitude is vital for successful educational outcomes at any age. Those with a positive attitude are more likely to be motivated, engage actively in the learning process, and persist in the face of difficulties. They are open to new ideas, willing to ask questions, and view mistakes as opportunities for growth. Conversely, a negative learning attitude can hinder educational progress. Factors such as low self-confidence, fear of failure, a lack of motivation, or a fixed mindset can impede a person's ability to fully engage with the learning material and reach their full potential (Ryan and Deci, 2000). It is important to note that while age and learning attitude play significant roles in education, they are not deterministic factors. People of any age can develop a positive learning attitude and achieve great educational outcomes with the right support, guidance, and access to appropriate learning opportunities. With the right mindset, motivation, and learning environment, learning can be a lifelong journey of growth and discovery for individuals of all ages (Fasching-Varner and Dennerlein, 2016).

In Gasaymeh, Kreishan, and Al-Dhaimat's (2014) study, 183 undergraduate and graduate students' attitudes toward academic group learning in computer training courses were examined in relation to their age, gender, and major. The study used a cross-sectional survey design. A non-significant association between students' attitudes and age toward academic group learning was found when researchers looked at the relationships between Jordanian students' attitudes toward academic group learning in computer training courses and their gender, age, and major. Additionally, Tůmová conducted a study in 2012 on how teachers' attitudes toward curriculum change were impacted by their age and amount of professional experience. For 1002 respondents, the age variable was not statistically significant when the variable of length of professional experience was. In a recent study, Akdemir (2019) looked into how age, gender, attitude, and motivation affected 239 participants' willingness

to listen (WTL) in L2. The results show that the mini-Attitude-Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) and WTL (with all aspects) scores of participants do not change significantly by age. Age was then found not to be a predictor of the attitude, motivation, and level of interest of EFL listeners in the study. Olutola, Ogunjimi, and Daramola (2021) further corroborated previous researchers findings that age, as a variable, is not significant in forecasting students' attitudes towards mathematics among selected public and private school students.

Gender and Learning Attitude

Gender can indeed have an impact on learning attitudes, although it is important to note that individual differences within each gender also play a significant role. Research has shown that there are some differences in learning attitudes between males and females (Cheng and Lai, 2013). One aspect to consider is the societal and cultural expectations that can shape gender roles and expectations (Eccles, Wigfield, and Schiefele, 1998). These expectations can influence learning attitudes in various ways. For example, girls may be more inclined to be cooperative and follow rules, which can lead to a greater emphasis on group work and collaborative learning. On the other hand, boys may be encouraged to be more competitive, leading to a preference for individual performance-based tasks.

Additionally, gender stereotypes can affect self-perception and confidence levels, which can affect learning attitudes. Research suggests that girls may be more likely to underestimate their abilities in certain subjects, such as math and science (Hyde and Linn, 2006), due to societal stereotypes (Nosek, Smyth, Sriram, Lindner, Devos, Ayala... Greenwald, 2009). This can result in lower self-efficacy and motivation in those areas. However, it is essential to note that these gender differences are not fixed or absolute. They can be influenced by various factors, including cultural context, educational environment, and individual experiences. Furthermore, there is considerable overlap between genders in terms of learning attitudes. Ultimately, it is crucial to recognize and address

individual differences rather than assuming that gender alone determines learning attitudes. By creating inclusive learning environments that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences, educators can help all students, regardless of their gender, develop positive learning attitudes and reach their full potential (Guimond, Chatard, Martinot, and Crisp, 2006).

In order to ascertain whether attitudes toward technology varied between males and females, a study on the impact of gender on attitudes, perceptions, and usage of technology was carried out by Bain and Rice (2006). Each sub-scale's posttest group means were determined, and a t-test with an independent sample was used to compare the means between females and males. Because there was no discernible difference in any of the subscales ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis was not rejected. Then, Chi-square analysis was conducted to see if there was a significant link between gender and how people perceived computer use. The null hypothesis was not rejected since no significant association between gender and perceptions of computer use was discovered ($p > .05$). The findings of this study suggest that students' attitudes toward technology are influenced by gender.

Areo (2022) used a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test methodology to examine the effects of gender on students' performance and attitudes about physics at secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study's conclusions showed that gender had no appreciable influence on students' physics proficiency. The null hypothesis was accepted as a result of this. The study's results also showed that students' opinions about physics were unaffected by their gender.

Cognitive Skills as a Measure of Learning

In Akanni (2021), Liu (2013) described cognitive skills as skills that are required in the human working mind. To succeed in the field of economics, several cognitive skills are necessary. These skills, with the right attitude, can boost the performance of economics students. These cognitive skills (Anderson, Reder, and Simon, 1996) are:

1. **Analytical thinking:** Economics involves analyzing complex data and identifying patterns, trends, and relationships. Having a positive attitude with strong analytical thinking skills will help students understand economic theories, models, and concepts and apply them to real-world scenarios.
2. **Quantitative reasoning:** Economics heavily relies on quantitative analyses and statistical methods. A strong foundation in mathematics and statistics is crucial for understanding economic relationships, forecasting trends, conducting research, and interpreting data.
3. **Logical reasoning:** sound logical reasoning skills are essential for understanding and constructing economic arguments. Students need to be able to assess cause-and-effect relationships, evaluate different perspectives, and make logical deductions in order to analyze economic situations effectively.
4. **Problem Solving:** Economics often involves tackling complex economic issues and developing feasible solutions. Effective problem-solving skills help young economists identify, analyze, and address economic challenges using economic theories, models, and empirical evidence.
5. **Critical thinking:** Economics requires critical thinking skills to evaluate and assess economic theories, policies, and arguments. Students need to be able to think critically about economic concepts, evaluate their strengths and weaknesses, and form evidence-based judgments.
6. **Data interpretation:** being able to interpret and analyze data is vital for economists. This includes understanding statistical measures, data visualization techniques, and conducting econometric analysis. Strong data interpretation skills will help you derive meaningful insights and support your economic analyses.
7. **Communication:** Economics involves conveying complex economic concepts in a clear and concise manner. Developing effective communication skills, both written and oral, is important for presenting economic analysis,

research findings, and policy recommendations to various audiences.

8. **Attention to Detail:** Economics deals with intricate theories, models, and datasets. Paying attention to detail is crucial for accurately interpreting economic data, identifying potential biases, and ensuring the validity of economic analysis.

While cognitive skills are important, they can be developed and honed over time through a positive attitude, practice, continuous learning, and real-world application.

Then, Akanni (2021) states that in order for pupils to succeed academically, their cognitive abilities must be completely utilized. His research shows that cognitive abilities like logical reasoning and abstract thought have a considerable impact on senior secondary school pupils' academic progress. This invariably means that if these traits of attitude are developed, there will be significant progress in the academic pursuit.

Affection for Learning Economics

An affection for learning is a deep-seated passion or fondness for acquiring knowledge, gaining new skills, and embracing the process of education. It is the inherent desire to explore and understand the world around us and to continually seek personal growth and development through learning. Having affection for learning goes beyond simply completing academic tasks or meeting educational requirements. It involves an intrinsic motivation to engage in lifelong learning, driven by genuine curiosity and a genuine love for acquiring knowledge. Here are a few reasons why cultivating affection for learning is important:

1. **Personal Growth:** Affection for learning stimulates personal growth by expanding one's horizons, broadening perspectives, and developing critical thinking skills. When we actively pursue knowledge, we enhance our understanding of the world, ourselves, and our place in it.

2. **Continuous Adaptation:** In today's rapidly changing world, being open to learning is crucial to adapting and thriving. An affection for

learning allows individuals to remain agile and adaptable, embracing new ideas, technologies, and opportunities with enthusiasm and confidence.

3. **Career Advancement** (Gamage, Dehideniya, and Ekanayake, 2021): Continued learning and skill development are vital for career advancement and professional success. Having an affection for learning enables individuals to stay updated with industry trends, acquire new skills, and enhance their expertise, increasing their value in the job market.

4. **Personal Satisfaction:** Learning can be an immensely fulfilling and gratifying experience. It satisfies our innate curiosity, boosts our self-esteem, and provides a sense of accomplishment. The joy of discovering new knowledge and mastering new skills is deeply rewarding, fostering personal satisfaction and fulfillment.

To nurture and enhance your affection for learning, the following tips should be considered:

1. **Follow your passions:** pursue topics and subjects that genuinely interest you. Learning becomes more enjoyable when you have a genuine passion for what you are studying. Explore different areas of knowledge and find what sparks your curiosity.

2. **Embrace Different Learning Styles** (Lei, 007): Everyone has a unique learning style. Experiment with various learning techniques such as reading, listening to podcasts, watching educational videos, doing hands-on activities, or joining study groups. Find the methods that work best for you and make the learning experience more enjoyable.

3. **Set Goals:** Establish clear goals and objectives for your learning journey. Whether it is completing a certification, learning a new language, or delving into a specific field, setting targets provides a sense of direction and achievement.

4. **Seek Diverse Experiences:** Engage in a variety of educational experiences, including attending workshops, conferences, or seminars. Explore different perspectives and challenge

your own beliefs and assumptions. Broadening your learning experiences can enrich your affection for learning.

5. Cultivate a growth mindset: embrace challenges and setbacks as opportunities for growth. A growth mindset entails believing in your capacity to learn and develop as well as realizing that intelligence and abilities may be improved through hard work and commitment.

In fact, developing and nourishing an affection for learning is a lifelong journey. Embrace curiosity, stay open-minded, and continue to explore and expand your intellectual horizons. In their classical study on the effect of affection on the method of teaching, Mohammadian and Dolatabadi (2016) discovered that the performance of mentally retarded pupils triples the outcome of the instruction. Lei (2007) in Mohammadian and Dolatabadi (2016) reveal that the positive influence of teachers on affections may boost students' language adeptness through interests, motivation, and attitude towards the language.

Bahri and Corebima (2015), in two Indonesian universities, conducted a correlational study on 142 students' cognitive learning outcomes between learning motivation and metacognitive skill. The composite contribution of the two variables was very high. Furthermore, metacognitive skills contribute significantly more to cognitive learning outcomes than learning motivation. In a similar study reported in Bahri and Corebima (2015), Mustaqim, Abdurrahman, and Viyanti (2013) also attested to the composite significance of metacognitive skill over students' learning motivation.

The Value Attached to Learning Economics

The place of value is very crucial in academic ventures and interventions since they reflect the beliefs that power behaviors, attitudes, and social norms (Gamage et al., 2021). Attached value or value attached then underpins the significance of conscious engagement in acquiring a particular project. Learning economics is valuable for multiple reasons:

1. Understanding the Economy: Economics helps individuals gain a deeper

understanding of how the economy functions, including factors such as production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services. This knowledge is essential for making informed decisions as consumers, investors, entrepreneurs, or policymakers.

2. Personal Finance: Economics equips individuals with the knowledge to manage their personal finances more effectively. It helps in making informed decisions about budgeting, investing, and saving for future goals. By understanding economic concepts like inflation, interest rates, and taxation, individuals can make better financial choices.

3. Career Opportunities (Gamage et al., 2021): Economics offers a broad range of career opportunities. It provides a strong foundation for pursuing fields such as finance, business, consulting, public policy, market research, and more. Economic literacy is highly sought after by employers due to the analytical and problem-solving skills developed through studying this subject.

4. Decision-Making Skills: Economics enhances critical thinking and decision-making abilities. It teaches individuals to assess and analyze different scenarios, weigh costs and benefits, and make rational choices based on available resources. These skills are valuable in both personal and professional lives.

5. Understanding Global Issues: Economics provides insights into global issues like international trade, poverty, inequality, and environmental concerns. It enables individuals to comprehend the interconnectedness of economies and the impact of policies on a global scale. Such understanding is crucial to addressing complex global challenges.

6. Policy Impact: Knowledge of economics empowers individuals to participate in policy discussions and contribute to societal changes. By evaluating the economic implications of policies, individuals can engage in informed debates and advocate for effective solutions to social, economic, and environmental issues.

7. Analyzing Current Events: Economics helps individuals interpret and analyze current

events through an economic lens. Whether it is understanding the causes and effects of economic crises, evaluating government economic interventions, or deciphering market trends, economic knowledge allows individuals to comprehend the broader implications of news and events.

In summary, learning economics provides individuals with a valuable set of skills and knowledge that can be applied in various aspects of life. It fosters economic literacy, critical thinking, and decision-making abilities while offering a wide range of career opportunities. Moreover, it enables individuals to understand and contribute to important global and societal issues.

Efforts in Learning Economics

To excel in learning economics, it is important to understand that it requires a considerable amount of effort and dedication. Economics can be a complex subject with various theories, concepts, and quantitative analyses involved. Here are some key factors that contribute to the effort required to learn economics:

1. **Time commitment:** Learning economics involves devoting sufficient time to understand and comprehend the theories and principles. This may include reading textbooks, researching academic articles, and solving practice problems.
2. **Active engagement:** Instead of passively consuming information, active engagement is crucial. This can involve taking notes, participating in class discussions, asking questions, and seeking clarification on any concepts that may be difficult to grasp.
3. **Practice and application:** Economics requires practical application and problem-solving skills. It is important to work through numerical exercises, case studies, and practical examples to reinforce concepts and enhance understanding.
4. **Analytical thinking:** Economics involves critical and analytical thinking. Developing these skills requires effort in terms of practicing logical reasoning, conducting research, and analyzing various economic scenarios.

5. **Continual learning:** Economics is a dynamic field, with new theories and concepts emerging over time. Staying updated with current research, reading academic journals, and attending seminars can help foster a deeper understanding and keep you at the forefront of economic knowledge.

6. **Seek guidance and support:** Learning economics can be challenging, so seeking guidance and support from professors, classmates, or online communities can greatly enhance the learning experience. Engaging in discussions, joining study groups, or seeking tutoring when necessary can make the learning process more manageable.

7. **Application in real-life situations:** Understanding how economics intersects with real-life situations and policies can deepen your understanding and make the subject matter more meaningful. Keeping up with economic news, analyzing economic events, and understanding their implications provide practical applications for the concepts learned.

Importantly, the effort you put into learning economics will determine not only your level of understanding but also your ability to apply economic principles in different contexts. Embrace the challenges, stay motivated, and persist in your learning journey to achieve success in economics. Effects of students' effort scores in a structured inquiry unit on long-term recall skills of content knowledge were examined by Schmid and Bogner (2015), an association between spent effort, usefulness, and high proficiency for learning the lesson's material was found. Students who felt they had a high level of skill in understanding the lesson's material scored well on effort and utility. Out of the three student characteristics tracked throughout their study, after six and twelve weeks, subject knowledge retention was positively impacted by effort alone. According to this, the students who made a concerted effort to behave decently while taking part in the inquiry class were also the ones who received the highest knowledge scores twelve weeks later. As a result, the students who gave the lesson their all were the ones who got the most out of the inquiry class. It was

discovered that a student's degree of effort during an inquiry) lesson may predict long-term performance for as long as at least 12 weeks, which is a sizable period.

Interest in Learning Economics

Having an interest in economics is a wonderful thing! Economics is a field that explores how societies allocate their scarce resources to fulfill their unlimited wants and needs. It encompasses the study of the production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services, as well as the behavior of individuals, firms, and governments in relation to these activities. Developing an interest in economics can benefit you in various ways. Firstly, it provides you with a deeper understanding of how the global economy functions and how different factors, such as government policies, international trade, and market forces, influence economic outcomes. This knowledge can enable you to make informed decisions about your personal finances, investments, and career choices.

Moreover, studying economics equips you with critical thinking and analytical skills. Economic models and theories help you analyze complex real-world problems, evaluate costs and benefits, and make reasoned judgments. These skills are highly valued in a wide range of professions, including finance, consulting, policy analysis, and entrepreneurship. Additionally, economics offers insights into important societal issues such as poverty, inequality, unemployment, and environmental sustainability. By studying economics, you can contribute to the development of effective policies and solutions to address these challenges and improve the overall well-being of individuals and communities.

To cultivate your interest in economics, you can start by reading introductory economics textbooks or taking online courses. This will provide you with a solid foundation and help you grasp key concepts and theories. Following current economic news and subscribing to reputable economic publications or blogs can also help you stay updated on the latest developments in the field. Furthermore, consider engaging in discussions and debates

with fellow economics enthusiasts. Joining economic clubs, attending seminars or webinars, and participating in online forums can facilitate intellectual exchange and deepen your understanding of different perspectives within economics.

Lastly, always remember to explore real-world applications of economics. Look for opportunities to connect economic principles to practical situations, such as analyzing market trends, evaluating the impact of policies, or investigating economic phenomena in your local community. By nurturing your interest in economics and continuously expanding your knowledge, you can develop a rewarding understanding of the world's intricate economic systems and contribute meaningfully to economic discussions and decision-making processes. As a subscale in Bain & Rice's (2006) study, interest in computers was not significant towards student attitude when $t = 1.776$ and $p = .081$. This reveals there was no significant relationship between interest and students attitudes toward computer use.

Difficulty of Learning Economics

The difficulty of learning economics can vary from person to person. While some individuals may find it relatively easy to grasp the concepts and theories, others may struggle due to the abstract nature and complexity of the subject. One of the factors that can make economics challenging is the extensive use of mathematical and statistical techniques. Understanding and applying these quantitative methods can be daunting for those who are not comfortable with numbers or lack a strong background in mathematics.

Additionally, economics requires critical thinking and analytical skills. It involves analyzing complex data, interpreting economic models, and drawing logical conclusions based on limited information. Developing this ability to think like an economist takes time and practice. Moreover, economics often deals with abstract concepts such as supply and demand, inflation, or fiscal policy, which may not have direct real-world counterparts or be easily observable. This can make it challenging to

connect theoretical concepts to practical situations. Furthermore, economics is a dynamic field that is constantly evolving. New theories, models, and policies emerge regularly, requiring individuals to stay updated with the latest developments. Keeping up with these changes can be demanding, especially for those who have limited time or resources for continuous learning.

However, with effective teaching strategies, proper resources, and dedication, the difficulty of learning economics can be overcome. Breaking down complex theories, providing real-world examples, and engaging in active learning methods can make the subject more accessible and enjoyable. Ultimately, with perseverance and a positive attitude toward learning, anyone can develop a solid understanding of economics.

Statement of the Problem

In practice, various instructional approaches have been employed to stimulate high and improved performances among secondary school students (SSS) offering economics, yet only a very slight improvement is being recorded. Considering this snail's performance, this study investigated the learning attitude of intermediate economics students in Oyo educational zone of Oyo State.

Research Questions

1. What influence does gender have on economics students' learning attitudes in Oyo Educational Zone?
2. What are the composite contributions of cognitive skills and affection for learning in the prediction of the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone?
3. What is the influence of attached value and effort in learning on Economics students' learning attitudes in Oyo Educational Zone?

Hypotheses

H₀1: There will be no significant influence of age on the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone.

H₀2: There will be no significant composite influence of interest and difficulties in learning

in the prediction of the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone.

Research Methodology

This study is survey research. It concentrated on the collected data with a view to describing the attributes found in the target population in a systematic way, with no intention to tamper with variables.

Population and Sample

The population of the study consisted of all Economics students in the intermediate class of Senior Secondary School 2 (SSS 2) in Oyo State. A multistage sampling procedure was used to select the participants. Four local government areas (LGAs), Afijio, Atiba, Oyo East, and Oyo West, were purposefully selected from the state as the LGAs of Oyo educational zone. Based on the number of schools in the zone, three (3) schools were randomly selected from each LGA. Twelve (12) schools participated in the survey. Finally, three hundred and fifty-five (355) students provide the sample for the study.

Instrumentation

The main instrument used in this study was the Economics Students' Learning Attitude Scale (ESLAS). ESLAS was an adapted version of Lee's (2013) SASS (Students' Attitudinal Scale for Statistics). The instrument consists of two sections. Section A comprises students' information, such as sex and age. Section B contains 29 items with six subheads on their attitudinal statements. When the instrument's reliability was tested using the Cronbach's alpha formula, a reliability coefficient of 0.808 was obtained; this value is regarded as reliable and suitable for the study.

Data Collection and Analysis

Researchers and research assistants administered the questionnaire to the students in the sampled schools. In order to address the issues posed by the study, various statistical analyses were conducted on the gathered data. These included inferential statistics like the t-test and analysis of

variance (ANOVA), as well as descriptive statistics like frequency counts and percentages.

Results and Discussion

Question 1: What influence does gender have on economics students' learning attitudes in Oyo Educational Zone?

Tables 1 present the investigation's findings, which are also briefly addressed in this section. Table 1a demonstrates that although learning attitude has a mean of 28.78 and a standard deviation of 3.93, gender has a mean and standard deviation of 1.65 and 0.48, respectively.

Table 2 shows Pearson correlation coefficients indicate that gender and learning attitude have an r of 0.05, a reflection of their significance ($p < .05$). The correlation coefficients serve as an

answer to research question 1 that was posed in the study. The findings indicate that gender has a major effect on Oyo Educational Zone economics students' learning attitudes. The reports of Bain & Rice (2006) and Areo (2022) were at variance with the findings of this study. Bain & Rice (2006) reveal that students' attitudes toward technology are predicted by gender's effect. On the other hand, Areo's (2022) study indicated that gender does not determine the attitude of students towards physics.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Gender of respondents	1.65	0.48	355
Learning Attitude	28.78	3.93	355

Table 2. Correlations

		Gender of respondents	Learning Attitude
Gender of respondents	Pearson Correlation	1	0.05
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.32
	N	355	355
Learning Attitude	Pearson Correlation	0.05	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.32	
	N	355	355

Question 2: What are the composite contributions of cognitive skills and affection for learning in the prediction of the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone?

According to Table 3, the multiple regression coefficient (R) is 0.714, the regression square (R^2) is 0.51, the corrected R^2 is 0.507, and the estimate's standard error is 2.756. Additionally, it illustrates the statistics of change, showing an R^2 change of 0.51 that shows the composite contributions—cognitive skills and an affection of learning—account for 51% of the variance in the criterion (learning attitude), and that this prediction is statistically significant ($p .05$) at 2 and 352 degrees of freedom (df). The data presented here provides an answer to research question number two.

Table 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.714 ^a	0.510	0.507	2.756

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affection, Cognitive

Table 4 (ANOVA) indicates the composite contributions of cognitive skills and affection for learning in the prediction of the learning attitude of Economics students, with a regression SS of 2778.248 and a MS of 1389.124. The residual SS is 2674.050 and 7.597 MS. The total SS is 5452.299. The resultant F of 182.858 is statistically significant.

Table 4. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2778.248	2	1389.124	182.858	0.000 ^b
	Residual	2674.050	352	7.597		
	Total	5452.299	354			
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Attitude						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Affection, Cognitive						

The unstandardized multiple regression is shown to have coefficients of 0.341 for cognitive skills and 1.460 for learning affection in Table 5 (coefficients). The standardized regression coefficients (Beta), which are used to test the relevance of each predictor variable's role in predicting the criterion variable, are of the utmost practical value. Affection for learning has a beta of 0.677 and a t of 17.868 that are both statistically significant ($p < .05$) in terms of cognitive capabilities and affection for learning, respectively. The composite contribution of cognitive skills and affection for learning is significant in predicting the learning attitude of economics students.

The combined outcome of this study is supported by Mustaqim et al. (2013) and Bahri and Corebima's (2015) reports on the correlated contribution of learning motivation and metacognitive competence to students' cognitive learning outcomes. This implies that when students do not have a phobia for calculation and enjoy an economics teaching session, their attitudes will support them in exhibiting the cognitive skills needed for success. Furthermore, contrary to Bahri and Corebima's (2015) in-depth analysis, metacognitive skills had a much greater contribution than learning motivation, while both cognitive skills and affection for learning in this study jointly contributed immensely to the significance of the result.

Table 5. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.761	1.326		5.852	0.000
	Cognitive	0.341	0.093	0.138	3.653	0.000
	Affection	1.460	0.082	0.677	17.868	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Attitude						

Question 3: What is the influence of attached value and efforts in learning on Economics students' learning attitudes in Oyo Educational Zone?

Table 7 shows that attached value and efforts in learning have means and standard deviations of 17.107 and 2.9506, and 12.8732 and 2.43868, respectively, while learning attitude has a $\bar{x}$ = 28.78 and SD = 3.925.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Std. Deviation (SD)	N
Value	17.1070	2.95060	355
Efforts	12.8732	2.43868	355
Learning Attitude	28.78	3.925	355

The correlation is significant at the two-tailed 0.01 level. Pairwise correlation coefficients are shown in Table 8, along with the actual significance level for each, showing:

1. Attached value and learning attempts have a significant ($p < .05$) correlation coefficient of 0.386.

2. Learning efforts and learning attitude have a significant ($p < .05$) correlation of 0.417.

3. Learning attitude and attached value have a significant ($p < .05$) correlation of 0.898.

As a result, it can be concluded that the Pearson's correlation coefficients of $r = 0.386$, 0.417 , and 0.898 with an N of 355 are statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p = 0.000$), and are obviously significant at the 0.05 level as well. Thus, the result reveals a significant influence of attached value and efforts in learning on the

learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone.

Schmid and Bogner (2015), who found a positive correlation between invested effort and usefulness on proficiency in learning the focus of the lesson, support the findings of this study. Furthermore, each construct in these studies significantly influences dependent variables. This suggests that students who put up an effort to learn economics would have attached additional value to the learning of economics with a positive attitude. Therefore, students who work hard to learn economic concepts and complete assignments will have developed a positive attitude toward the subject.

Table 8. Correlations

		Value	Efforts	Learning Attitude
Attached Value	Pearson Correlation	1	0.386**	0.898**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
	N	355	355	355
Efforts	Pearson Correlation	0.386**	1	0.417**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
	N	355	355	355
Learning Attitude	Pearson Correlation	0.898**	0.417**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	
	N	355	355	355

The significance level for the ** correlation is 0.01 (2-tailed).

Research Hypothesis

H₀1: There will be no significant influence of age on the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone.

In Table 9, a one-way between-subjects ANOVA was conducted on the influence of age on the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone. This revealed a statistically non-significant influence on the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone in terms of age, with a difference between groups' SS of 27.547 and MS

of 13.774. Within groups, SS is 5424.751 and 15.411 MS. The total SS is 5452.299. The resultant F of 0.894 is not statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The findings of Tumorová, A. (2012), Gasaymeh et al. (2014), Akdemir (2019), and Olutola et al. (2021) that age is not a predictor of major influence on students' learning attitudes are thus corroborated by those studies. This reveals that age has nothing to do with the prediction of learning attitudes in economics.

Table 9. ANOVA

	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F	Sig.
Between Groups	27.547	2	13.774	.894	.410
Within Groups	5424.751	352	15.411		
Total	5452.299	354			

Table 10. Multiple Comparisons

(I) Age of respondents	(J) Age of respondents	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Below 15 years	15-18 years	-.559	.612	.362	-1.76	.65
	19-20 years	.404	1.045	.699	-1.65	2.46
15-18 years	Below 15 years	.559	.612	.362	-.65	1.76
	19-20 years	.963	.908	.290	-.82	2.75
19-20 years	Below 15 years	-.404	1.045	.699	-2.46	1.65
	15-18 years	-.963	.908	.290	-2.75	.82

Table 10 reveals that in 15–18 years, there is a high mean difference between below 15 years and 19–20 years of 0.559 and 0.963, respectively.

H₀2: There is no significant composite influence of interest and difficulties in learning in the prediction of the learning attitude of economics students in Oyo Educational Zone.

According to Table 11, the multiple regression coefficient (R) is 0.534, the regression square (R²) is 0.286, the adjusted R² is 0.282, and the estimate's standard error is 3.326. Additionally, it demonstrates the statistics of change, which show that R² change is 0.286 and that the composite contributions (interest and learning challenges) jointly account for 28.6% of the variance in the criterion (learning attitude). This prediction is statistically significant (p .05) at 2 and 352 degrees of freedom (df). The null hypothesis is thus disproved, and there is a strong combined influence of interest and learning challenges on the prediction of the learning attitude of Economics students in the Oyo Educational Zone.

This finding is in line with Kpolovie et al.'s (2014) report of the appealing influence of interest in learning in predicting academic performance, and that interest is an indisputable psychological construct. In a similar study, Paul (2013) discovered that interest significantly energized students to learn in spite of all odds, thereby propelling a positive attitude toward learning. Then, students will be interested in communicating and learning new topics and concepts in economics.

Table 11. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.534 ^a	0.286	0.282	3.326
a. Predictors: (Constant), Difficulty, Interest				

Table 12 indicates the composite influence of interest and difficulties in learning in the prediction of learning attitudes in economics Students in Oyo Educational Zone have a regression SS of 1557.243 and a MS of 778.621. The residual SS is 3895.056 and the residual MS is 11.065. The total SS is 5452.299. The resultant F of 70.365 is statistically significant.

Table 12. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1557.243	2	778.621	70.365	0.000 ^b
	Residual	3895.056	352	11.065		
	Total	5452.299	354			
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Attitude						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Difficulty, Interest						

As a last example, Table 13 (coefficients) displays the unstandardized multiple regression of 0.770 for interest and 0.067 for difficulties with learning. The standardized regression coefficients (Beta), which are used to test the relevance of each predictor variable's role in predicting the criterion variable, are of the utmost practical value. While the beta for interest is 0.042 with a t of 0.803 that is not statistically significant ($p < .05$), the beta for

learning difficulties is 0.042 with a t of 0.803 that is. Although there is a significant composite contribution of interest and difficulties in predicting learning attitude, interest, as a variable, greatly contributes more than difficulties in learning. This in-depth fact corroborates Bahri and Corebima's (2015) in-depth analysis, where one variable statistically contributes more than the other combined variable.

Table 13. Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.338	1.364		11.246	0.000
	Interest	0.770	0.079	0.512	9.741	0.000
	Difficulties	0.067	0.083	0.042	0.803	0.423

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Attitude

Based on the survey, the findings of this investigation show that:

1. Gender's influence is significant on the learning attitude of Economics students in Oyo Educational Zone, as discovered.
2. The composite contribution of cognitive skills and affection for learning is significant in predicting the learning attitude of economics students.
3. A significant influence of attached value and efforts in learning on the learning attitude of Economics students was observed in Oyo Educational Zone.
4. Economics students' age has no significant influence on their learning attitude in Oyo Educational Zone.
5. There is a significant composite influence of interest and difficulties in learning as predictors of learning attitude among intermediate economics students in Oyo Educational Zone.

Conclusion

Based on the findings and discussion, appropriate deductions were drawn that this investigation has revealed vast proof that while gender tends to influence learning attitude, a student's age does not. The predictors must have strong correlations with both themselves and learning attitude individually and collectively in order to significantly predict learning attitude. The prediction of learning attitude implies that there is a great need for students to be proactive in learning, as this would improve their cognitive skills, affection, attached value, efforts, and interest in learning while reducing difficulties and challenges to the barest minimum.

Recommendations

1. Teachers of economics should strive to pique their students' interest.
2. It is recommended that teachers should approach the teaching of Economics with required cognitive approaches to stimulate students' affection, attached value and interest in learning Economics.

3. Students should make frantic efforts to overcome challenges and difficulties in learning economics.
4. While cognitive skills, affection, attached value, efforts, and interest in learning, as psychological constructs, significantly predict learning attitude, school management and relevant authorities in administration should organize workshops and seminars for teachers.

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